

Evaluation of the Peroxone Process in a Multiphase Flow Reactor for Enhanced Micropollutant Removal

J. F. Mata De la Vega*, K. Nasr Esfahani*, T. Mao**, P. Roccaro***, and D. Santoro*

* Department of Chemical & Biochemical Engineering, Western University, ON, N6A 5B9, London, Canada

** MW Technologies, London Ontario, Canada

*** Department of Civil Engineering and Architecture, University of Catania, Viale A. Doria 6, 95125 Catania, Italy

(E-mail: dsantor@uwo.ca)

Abstract

This study investigates the peroxone process—a combination of hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) and ozone (O_3)—in a flow chemistry-based reactor, MITO₃X[®]. The objective was to evaluate the efficiency of hydroxyl radical ($\cdot\text{OH}$) production under various operational parameters, including pump frequency, water flow rate, and ozone mass concentration. Experiments revealed that 89% of injected ozone dissolved into the water stream, enabling effective reaction with hydrogen peroxide. Residual concentrations of ozone and hydrogen peroxide were measured to determine the reacted quantities of each reagent. Results highlight the synergistic interaction between O_3 and H_2O_2 , demonstrating significant potential for advanced oxidation processes in wastewater treatment applications.

Keywords

Advanced oxidation processes; micropollutant degradation; ozonation; pressure intensification; wastewater treatment;

INTRODUCTION

The increasing presence of micropollutants in wastewater necessitates advanced treatment technologies. The peroxone process, which combines ozone (O_3) and hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2), enhances hydroxyl radical ($\cdot\text{OH}$) production, making it a promising solution for degrading recalcitrant contaminants. Theoretically, two moles of O_3 react per one mole of H_2O_2 to yield two moles of $\cdot\text{OH}$ and three moles of oxygen (Zheng et al., 2013).

However, the application of ozone in wastewater treatment faces challenges such as limited solubility, rapid decomposition, and high operational costs (Nasr Esfahani et al., 2024). Enhancing ozone mass transfer through optimized reactor design is essential for maximizing contaminant degradation. Increased operational pressure improves ozone solubility and reduces gas-phase losses, leading to better dissolution and degradation efficiency (Wang et al., 2021). Recent advancements, like the MITO₃X[®] system, address these limitations by improving mixing, particle disaggregation, and mass transfer rates. This innovative technology offers the potential to enhance process efficiency, lower capital and operational expenses, and eliminate the need for additional mixing infrastructure (Murgolo et al., 2024).

This study examines the multiphase reaction of O_3 and H_2O_2 in the MITO₃X[®] reactor, a flow chemistry-based system designed to optimize mass transfer and mixing. By evaluating the influence of operational parameters on the peroxone reaction, the research aims to identify conditions that maximize hydroxyl radical production and contaminant degradation efficiency. The novelty of this work lies in applying a multiphase flow reactor concept, originally developed for fine chemical synthesis, to the peroxone process, enabling near-instantaneous ozone dissolution and intensified radical generation within a single pass.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental setup

The MITO₃X[®] reactor, as shown in Figure 1, was configured with multiphase centrifugal pumps and gas injection units to facilitate the dissolution of ozone into the water stream. Operational conditions included pump frequency of 60 Hz, water flow rate of 50 L/min, and two ozone mass concentrations (54 and 120 g O₃/hr). Hydrogen peroxide was injected at a controlled rate of 9.2–9.7 mg H₂O₂/hr.

Figure 1. Ozone system scheme (MITO₃X[®] reactor).

Analytical Measurements

The 1000-gallon inlet tank was filled with dechlorinated tap water spiked with target contaminants, including methylene blue (3–5 ppm), 4-chlorobenzoic acid (500 ppb), and select pharmaceuticals (e.g., caffeine, acetaminophen, ciprofloxacin, carbamazepine, sulfamethoxazole, and erythromycin) at varying concentrations. Ozone residuals were quantified using the Chemetrics Ozone Vacu-vials Kit K-7423 and a Hach DR3900 Spectrophotometer, with absorbance measurements at 515 nm following sample activation with A-7400 solution. The hydrogen peroxide residual test was carried out using the Hach Method 10290: with the Hach DR3900 Spectrophotometer with a H₂O₂ preset method using 530 nm. All reagents were purchased through Hach.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results were compared through the performance of an H₂O₂/O₃ system with an O₃-only control for pollutant degradation. As Figure 2(a) displays the residual ozone concentrations in both systems (H₂O₂/O₃ and control), the residual ozone concentrations in the O₃-alone system increased with higher ozone injection, particularly above 20 ppm. In contrast, the H₂O₂/O₃ system exhibited higher residual ozone at lower injected concentrations (<20 ppm), but levels remained low as ozone injection increased, indicating greater ozone consumption due to micropollutant degradation.

Additional follow in Figure 2(b), the consumption of ozone aligned with increased reacted H₂O₂ levels (10–15 ppm injected ozone), highlighting the synergistic interaction between H₂O₂ and O₃ in enhancing oxidative reactions. The combined data suggest that the H₂O₂/O₃ system promotes more efficient ozone utilization for contaminant degradation compared to ozone alone. Additionally, the

higher reactivity in the $\text{H}_2\text{O}_2/\text{O}_3$ system may enable improved pollutant removal under optimized operating conditions. This behavior underscores the synergistic interaction between hydrogen peroxide and ozone in advanced oxidation processes (Tan et al., 2024).

Figure 2. a) Residual ozone concentrations in the $\text{H}_2\text{O}_2/\text{O}_3$ system compared to the O_3 -only control under varying ozone injection levels. b) Relationship between residual ozone and reacted H_2O_2 in the $\text{H}_2\text{O}_2/\text{O}_3$ system.

Pollutant removal in the $\text{H}_2\text{O}_2/\text{O}_3$ system depended on the reacted amounts of ozone and hydrogen peroxide. Figure 3 illustrates the interaction of reacted O_3 and H_2O_2 with pCBA (as an example from the set of micropollutants) in the $\text{H}_2\text{O}_2/\text{O}_3$ system. Figure 3(a) shows that at ozone concentrations of 10 ppm or higher, pCBA was completely degraded, indicating a strong correlation between ozone capacity and pollutant removal. Furthermore, the color bar indicating ozone capacity reinforces the notion that higher ozone levels directly correlate with improved pollutant removal, provided the ozone reacts efficiently with the target compounds.

Figure 3(b) highlights the relationship between reacted hydrogen peroxide and pCBA degradation, demonstrating that increased H_2O_2 reaction corresponds to greater pollutant removal, particularly when paired with sufficient reacted ozone levels.

Figure 3. Interaction of reacted O_3 and H_2O_2 with pCBA (c/c_0) in the $\text{H}_2\text{O}_2/\text{O}_3$ system. a) Relationship between reacted ozone and pCBA degradation, with the color bar representing ozone capacity. b) Correlation between reacted H_2O_2 and pCBA degradation, with the color bar indicating the corresponding levels of reacted ozone.

Increasing levels of reacted H_2O_2 result in greater removal of pCBA, particularly when complemented by adequate reacted ozone levels. The interplay between these two reagents indicates that hydrogen peroxide serves as a critical co-reagent, enhancing the generation of hydroxyl radicals and facilitating the oxidation of micropollutants. This synergistic effect between ozone and hydrogen peroxide demonstrates the potential of the $\text{H}_2\text{O}_2/\text{O}_3$ system to achieve higher removal efficiencies for a broad spectrum of contaminants, even at lower pollutant concentrations. These findings underscore the importance of optimizing both ozone and hydrogen peroxide dosages to maximize the overall efficiency of advanced oxidation processes (Khan et al., 2023).

CONCLUSIONS

This study assessed the efficacy of the peroxone process in a flow-based reactor, MITO₃X[®], for enhanced micropollutant removal. The combination of ozone and hydrogen peroxide demonstrated significant potential for degrading micropollutants, with operational parameters playing a critical role in process efficiency. The aim of Experiment phase was to investigate the multiphase reaction of two reagents, hydrogen peroxide and ozone in the flow chemistry-based reactor. By leveraging the advanced design of the MITO₃X[®] reactor, this research paves the way for scalable and cost-effective solutions in wastewater treatment.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This study was supported under the scholarship provided by the government of Mexico and State of Guanajuato through the National Council of Science and Technology (CONACYT) and the Instituto para el Desarrollo y Atención a las Juventudes del Estado de Guanajuato. The study was also partially supported by the European Union (NextGeneration EU), through the MUR-PNRR project SAMOTHRACE (ECS00000022).

REFERENCES

- Khan, Z. U. H., Gul, N. S., Sabahat, S., Sun, J., Tahir, K., Shah, N. S., Muhammad, N., Rahim, A., Imran, M., Iqbal, J., Khan, T. M., Khasim, S., Farooq, U., & Wu, J. 2023 Removal of organic pollutants through hydroxyl radical-based advanced oxidation processes. *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety*, 267, 115564.
- Murgolo, S., De Giglio, O., De Ceglie, C., Triggiano, F., Apollonio, F., Calia, C., Pousis, C., Marzella, A., Fasano, F., Giordano, M. E., Lionetto, M. G., Santoro, D., Santoro, O., Mancini, S., Di Iaconi, C., De Sanctis, M., Montagna, M. T., & Mascolo, G. 2024 Multi-target assessment of advanced oxidation processes-based strategies for indirect potable reuse of tertiary wastewater: Fate of compounds of emerging concerns, microbial and ecotoxicological parameters. *Environmental Research*, 241, 117661.
- Nasr Esfahani, K., Santoro, D., Pérez-Moya, M., & Graells, M. 2024 Mathematical modeling of ozone decomposition processes in wastewater treatment: A lumped kinetic approach with initial ozone demand. *Journal of Environmental Chemical Engineering*, 12(6), 114893.
- Tan, S., Long, K., Chen, W., Liu, H., Liang, S., & Zhang, Q. 2024 Synergistic oxidation of humic acid treated by $\text{H}_2\text{O}_2/\text{O}_3$ activated by CuCo/C with high efficiency and wide pH range. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 358, 120896.
- Wang, B., Shi, W., Zhang, H., Ren, H., & Xiong, M. 2021 Promoting the ozone-liquid mass transfer through external physical fields and their applications in wastewater treatment: A review. *Journal of Environmental Chemical Engineering*, 9(5), 106115.
- Zheng, C., Zhao, L., Zhou, X., Fu, Z., & Li, A. 2013 Treatment Technologies for Organic Wastewater (W. Elshorbagy & R. K. Chowdhury (eds.); p. Ch. 11). IntechOpen.